

ERRATUM

In the article

FRANCK BOYER, 2003. The Cystiscidae (Caenogastropoda) from upper reef formations of New Caledonia". *Iberus*, 21 (1): 241-272.

a wrong numbering was introduced within the second plate of figures. The numbering attached to the pictures must be changed as following:

n° 20 becomes n° 18

n° 18 becomes n° 19

n° 21 becomes n° 20

n° 19 becomes n° 21

The numbering used in the text and in the captions are right.